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TORTS OFFENSES: HOW TO EFFECTIVELY DEFEND CLIENTS' INTERESTS IN COURT

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ABSTRACT

The article analyzes torts offenses (TO). It highlights various types of TO and their legal regulation. The laws and principles regulating tort law are discussed, along with effective defense methods of clients' interests in court such as comparative negligence and challenging causation. To demonstrate the practical application of these strategies, cases such as *Martex Corp. v. Artilis*, the multidistrict Formula NEC litigation, and PFAS Contamination lawsuits are analyzed.

Keywords: tort offenses, civil litigation, legal principles, legal defense, negligence, intentional torts, strict liability.

Introduction

Torts offenses (TO), commonly referred to as civil wrongs, encompass a vast area of law, integral to the judicial resolution of conflicts in personal, professional, and societal domains.

The relevance of this research stems from the increasing complexity of civil litigation (CL), underscored by evolving legal norms, societal values, and technological advancements that continually reshape the landscape of civil law.

TO encompass a broad range of legal violations where an individual's actions, either through negligence, intent, or strict liability, cause harm or loss to

another party. The consequences of such violations often lead to legal disputes requiring adept navigation through legal frameworks and precedents to safeguard clients' interests effectively.

The purpose of this article is to analyze TO with the aim of identifying effective mechanisms for protecting the interests of clients in court.

Main part

The majority of torts are under the jurisdiction of state courts. According to the Court Statistics Project (CSP), in 2022, the number of torts in the USA amounted to about 6% of civil cases (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Distribution of types of appeals to state courts for 2015 and 2022, % [1]

Some torts end up in federal court because of differences in jurisdiction (when the defendant and plaintiff are residents of different states, and the amount of

the dispute exceeds \$75,000.00). According to the analytical firm Lex Machina, in 2022, USA federal district courts handled 14,376 TO (fig. 2).

Figure 2. TO from 2013 to 2022, Lex Machina [2]

From 2020 to 2022, the total amount of damages in the amount of 3.4 billion dollars in 234 cases was awarded as total compensation in TO [2].

Types of TO. The realm of TO, a critical component of torts litigation (TL), encompasses a diverse range of legal violations, each bearing distinct legal implications. These offenses, categorized based on the nature

of the wrongful act and the type of liability incurred, play a significant role in shaping the landscape of CL. The table below outlines the primary types of TO along with their legal implications, providing a concise overview of this complex area of law.

Table 1

Types of TO and their legal implications

Type of TO	Definition	Legal implications
Negligence	Failure to exercise the standard of care that a reasonably prudent person would in similar circumstances.	Liability for damages caused by the breach of duty of care.
Intentional torts	Deliberate actions that cause harm to another, such as assault, battery, or defamation.	Liability for actual damages and, in some cases, punitive damages.
Strict liability	Liability that does not depend on actual negligence or intent to harm, commonly applied in cases involving abnormally dangerous activities.	Liability for damages without the need to prove negligence or intent.

TL is also characterized by various defenses that can mitigate or nullify liability, such as consent, self-defense, and statutory limitations. The statute of limitations, for instance, sets a time limit within which a tort claim can be filed, as seen in various jurisdictions, which can vary depending on the nature of the TO and the jurisdiction.

Legal framework of TO. In the USA, TL is primarily governed by state law, although some federal statutes also apply. Notably, the legal landscape of TL in the USA includes a blend of common law principles and specific statutes:

- Federal Tort Claims Act allows for certain lawsuits against the USA for torts committed by persons acting on behalf of the government [3].
- 42 U.S.C. 1983: this federal law is a common basis for civil rights lawsuits, allowing individuals to sue for a variety of constitutional violations, including police misconduct [4].
- Restatement of Torts (2nd): while not a law per se, this is a highly influential guide used by many courts to interpret TL [5]. It provides a summary of the general principles of American TL, including categories like negligence, strict liability, and intentional torts.
- Comparative and contributory negligence: these are state-specific laws that apportion damages based on the degree of fault of each party involved in a tort. The specific rules vary from state to state.
- State-specific TL: each state has its own set of TL, which can include specific statutes on issues like medical malpractice, defamation, and privacy.

TL is built on common law principles, developed through judiciary decisions over time. This case-law

system allows for a dynamic and adaptable legal structure, capable of responding to new types of harms and societal changes.

Effective defense strategies in TO. In the realm of torts litigation, mounting an effective defense is paramount to protecting clients' interests. In legal proceedings, defense strategies are intricately tailored to the specific type of alleged misconduct, whether it involves intention, negligence, negligence per se, or strict liability. In cases of intentional wrongs, the defense often hinges on disproving the element of intent, arguing that the action was accidental or misunderstood, rather than deliberate. For negligence claims, the focus typically shifts to challenging the breach of duty or the causation link, suggesting that the defendant's conduct was reasonable under the circumstances or that an external factor was responsible for the harm. When recklessness is alleged, the defense strategy might involve showing that the defendant did not act with complete disregard for others' safety. In strict liability situations, where fault is not a prerequisite for liability, defenses often center on specific exceptions or mitigating circumstances that could exempt the defendant from liability. Each type of tort necessitates a unique approach, with the overarching aim of meticulously discrediting the plaintiff's evidence and safeguarding the client's interests.

Effective defense strategies must not only address the specificities of each case but also anticipate and counter the arguments and evidence presented by the opposing party (table 2).

Table 2.

Effective strategies for defending clients' interests in court.

Defense strategy	Description	Application
Affirmative defenses - depends on the kind and type of the tort		
Comparative and contributory negligence	Argues that the plaintiff was partly (or entirely) responsible for their own injuries.	Commonly used in personal injury cases where the plaintiff's own negligence contributed to the harm suffered.
Assumption of risk	Asserts that the plaintiff knowingly and voluntarily assumed the risk inherent in a dangerous activity.	Often applied in cases involving sports injuries or recreational activities.
Consent	Claims that the plaintiff consented to the conduct that led to the injury.	Used in cases where the plaintiff agreed to the possibility of harm.
Statute of limitations	Argues that the plaintiff filed the lawsuit outside of the legally prescribed time limit.	Applicable in almost all tort cases; time limits vary by state and type of tort.
Sovereign immunity	Government entities claim immunity from lawsuits unless they have consented to be sued.	Used in cases against government agencies or officials.
Self-defense/defense of others	Justifies the defendant's actions as necessary to protect themselves or others from harm.	Relevant in cases involving claims of assault or battery.
Other types of defenses		
Lack of duty/Breach	Argues that the defendant did not owe a duty of care to the plaintiff or did not breach that duty.	Central in negligence cases where establishing duty and breach is crucial.
No causation	Contends that the defendant's actions did not cause the plaintiff's harm.	Important in cases where there is a disconnect between the defendant's actions and the plaintiff's injuries.
No damages	Asserts that the plaintiff did not suffer any compensable harm.	Used when the plaintiff fails to prove that they suffered actual damages.
Privilege	Asserts a legal right to act in a certain way, such as in the case of defamation where the statement was a privileged communication.	Specific to certain torts like defamation or invasion of privacy.

Effective defense strategies in TL require a deep understanding of legal principles, astute application of defenses, and an ability to adapt to the unique circumstances of each case. In the legal domain, defending a client's interests often involves challenging the sufficiency of evidence for one or more elements of a tort claim. A tort is a civil wrong, and to establish liability, the plaintiff must prove four essential elements: duty, breach, causation, and damages:

- **Duty:** this is the legal obligation to adhere to a standard of reasonable care. The plaintiff must demonstrate that the defendant owed them a duty of care in the specific situation.
- A breach occurs when the defendant fails to meet the standard of care, which can be through action or inaction. The plaintiff must prove that the defendant's conduct deviated from what a reasonably prudent person would have done under similar circumstances.
- Causation links the breach of duty to the harm suffered. There are two types: actual cause (or cause in fact), which is a direct link between the defendant's action and the harm, and proximate cause, which relates to whether the harm was a foreseeable consequence of the defendant's action.
- **Damages:** the plaintiff must prove that they suffered actual harm or loss, which can be physical, emotional, or financial. This element aims to quantify the impact of the tort in compensable terms.

Each tort has its unique standards for proving these elements. The defense's strategy often focuses on casting doubt on the plaintiff's evidence regarding one or more of these elements. For example, in a negligence case, if the defense can show that the harm was not a foreseeable result of the defendant's actions (challenging proximate causation), it can significantly weaken the plaintiff's case. Similarly, if the defense can demonstrate that the plaintiff did not suffer any actual damages, the claim may fail despite the presence of the other three elements.

A successful defense in a tort case often revolves around meticulously scrutinizing and challenging the evidence presented for each of these elements, aiming to protect the client's interests by preventing the establishment of liability.

TO: judicial practice.

One notable example of a tort law case in California is the *Sheen v. Wells Fargo Bank* case, ruled by the California Supreme Court, March 7, 2022 [6]. The case focused on the tort liability of lenders and servicers in the context of handling loan modification applications. Specifically, the California Supreme Court addressed whether these entities owed a duty of care to borrowers in processing, reviewing, and responding to loan modification applications. The court ultimately decided that lenders and servicers are not liable for causing purely monetary losses to borrowers due to a lack of care in

handling their loan modification applications. This decision provided significant relief to lenders and servicers, as it limited their tort liability in such situations.

Another example is the case of Reyes Daniel Ruiz, ruled by the United States district court, Northern District of California, June 29, 2020 [7]. He was a software engineer at Yahoo and misused his access to hack into nearly 6,000 Yahoo user accounts. Ruiz's primary objective was to find sexually explicit images and videos. Ruiz didn't limit his activities to Yahoo accounts alone; using information obtained from these accounts, he also accessed the users' iCloud, Gmail, Facebook, DropBox, and other online services. He was indicted and charged with computer intrusion and interception of a wire communication. However, he pled guilty to a single count of computer intrusion. Despite the potential for a five-year prison sentence and a \$250,000 fine, he was sentenced to probation and home confinement for five years, a \$5,000 fine, and ordered to pay \$118,456 in restitution. His cooperation with the authorities and the fact that he didn't distribute the stolen content or attempt to contact his victims were factors in his sentencing. The case of Reyes Daniel Ruiz hacking into Yahoo user accounts represents a clear instance of trespass in the digital realm, where unauthorized access to personal information in email accounts was made.

Formula NEC (necrotizing enterocolitis) multidistrict litigation pending in the federal court focuses on cow's milk-based infant formulas and their alleged link to NEC in premature newborns [8]. The plaintiffs are parents and their premies who developed NEC after being fed cow's milk products, suing formula manufacturers for negligent failure to warn despite knowledge of the risks. This case is significant as it involves complex product liability issues and highlights the intersection of medical research and legal responsibility.

PFAS Contamination Lawsuits: this mass tort involves numerous lawsuits brought by individuals, state governments, and local municipalities against manufacturers of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS). These «forever chemicals» have been linked to various health risks, including cancer [9]. The litigation has particularly focused on the exposure of firefighters to PFAS through flame-retardant firefighting gear and firefighting foam. In September 2022, the US District Court for the District of South Carolina denied the defendant government contractors' motion for summary judgment, marking a significant development in the ongoing litigation. The case is crucial for understanding the liability of manufacturers for the long-term environmental and health impacts of their products.

One of the most significant mass litigation processes is ongoing from 2022 to 2024. For over 30 years, military personnel, their families, and civilians living and working at the Marine Corps Base Camp Lejeune were potentially exposed to contaminated drinking water. As of January 2024, more than 160,000 administrative cases (out of 13 settlements) have been filed [10].

Each of these cases provides insight into different aspects of TL, including premises liability, product liability, and environmental torts, illustrating the diverse nature of tort litigation.

Conclusions

The analysis of TO in this article emphasizes the multifaceted nature of CL, highlighting various types and implications of TO, including negligence, intentional torts, and strict liability. The diverse range of legal violations underscores the complexity of TO and their significant impact on the judicial resolution of personal, professional, and societal conflicts. The article's exploration of the legal framework of TO in the USA, including the Federal Tort Claims Act and state-specific TL, provides an understanding of the principles and statutes shaping the landscape of civil litigation.

Effective defense strategies in TL are crucial for safeguarding clients' interests. Strategies like comparative and contributory negligence in negligence torts, assumption of risk, and other affirmative defenses and challenging causation play a role in mitigating liability. The article also illustrates these strategies through judicial practice. Cases demonstrate the application of defense strategies in various contexts, highlighting the need for a deep understanding of legal principles, the astute application of defenses, and the ability to adapt to unique case circumstances in tort litigation.

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